

Figure S1. Spatial distribution of the Emberger Q1 classes for the reference period (1970-2000) over the phytogeographical zones of Greece.

Figure S2. Q1 classes' relative surface (1.0=100%) per phytogeographical zone for the reference period (1970-2000).

Table S1. The percentage (%) of the Q1 classes' coverage per phytogeographical zone for the 1970-2000 period.

	SeAr	SuHu	Hu	PeHu
Pe	1.4	88.4	10.2	0.0
NC	48.6	51.1	0.3	0.0
EAe	0.8	98.6	0.6	0.0
lol	0.0	35.2	64.8	0.0
EC	28.7	61.8	9.4	0.1
KK	0.0	74.7	23.6	1.7
NAe	58.3	41.7	0.0	0.0
KiK	67.2	32.8	0.0	0.0
WAe	56.0	44.0	0.0	0.0
NE	68.1	31.9	0.0	0.0
SPi	0.0	69.9	30.1	0.0
StE	10.7	83.6	5.7	0.0
NPi	0.0	63.6	36.3	0.1

Figure S3. Spatial distribution of the Emberger Q1 classes for the RCP4.5 scenario and 2021-2040 period over the phytogeographical zones of Greece.

Figure S4. Q1 classes' relative surface (1.0=100%) per phytogeographical zone for the RCP4.5 scenario and 2021-2040 period.

Table S2. The percentage (%) of the Q1 classes' coverage per phytogeographical zone for the RCP4.5 scenario and 2021-2040 period.

	SeAr	SuHu	Hu	PeHu
Pe	1.8	92.8	5.4	0.0
NC	59.0	40.9	0.1	0.0
EAe	0.7	99.1	0.2	0.0
lol	0.0	46.9	53.1	0.0
EC	34.3	59.4	6.3	0.0
KK	0.0	78.3	21.4	0.3
NAe	68.0	32.0	0.0	0.0
KiK	70.2	29.8	0.0	0.0
W Ae	59.3	40.7	0.0	0.0
NE	83.6	16.4	0.0	0.0
SPi	0.0	81.9	18.1	0.0
St E	11.5	86.0	2.5	0.0
NPi	0.0	75.2	24.8	0.0

Figure S5. Spatial distribution of the Emberger Q1 classes for the RCP4.5 scenario and 2041-2060 period over the phytogeographical zones of Greece.

Figure S6. Q1 classes' relative surface (1.0=100%) per phytogeographical zone for the RCP4.5 scenario and 2041-2060 period.

Table S3. The percentage (%) of the Q1 classes' coverage per phytogeographical zone for the RCP4.5 scenario and 2041-2060 period.

	SeAr	SuHu	Hu	PeHu
Pe	1.7	95.3	3.0	0.0
NC	68.6	31.4	0.0	0.0
EAe	2.1	97.9	0.0	0.0
lol	0.0	73.2	26.8	0.0
EC	37.6	58.6	3.8	0.0
KK	0.0	80.0	20.0	0.0
NAe	79.1	20.9	0.0	0.0
KiK	74.6	25.4	0.0	0.0
WAE	61.1	38.9	0.0	0.0
NE	89.7	10.3	0.0	0.0
SPi	1.7	92.0	6.3	0.0
StE	11.4	87.4	1.2	0.0
NPi	0.0	82.4	17.6	0.0

Figure S7. Spatial distribution of the Emberger Q1 classes for the RCP8.5 scenario and 2021-2040 period over the phytogeographical zones of Greece.

Figure S8. Q1 classes' relative surface (1.0=100%) per phytogeographical zone for the RCP8.5 scenario and 2021-2040 period.

Table S4. The percentage (%) of the Q1 classes' coverage per phytogeographical zone for the RCP8.5 scenario and 2021-2040 period.

	SeAr	SuHu	Hu	PeHu
Pe	1.8	93.8	4.4	0.0
NC	64.2	35.8	0.0	0.0
EAe	2.1	97.7	0.2	0.0
lol	0.0	67.0	33.0	0.0
EC	36.4	58.9	4.7	0.0
KK	0.0	78.7	21.2	0.1
NAe	75.7	24.3	0.0	0.0
KiK	72.6	27.4	0.0	0.0
W Ae	61.8	38.2	0.0	0.0
NE	87.6	12.4	0.0	0.0
SPi	0.3	89.4	10.3	0.0
St E	11.6	86.6	1.8	0.0
NPi	0.0	79.6	20.4	0.0

Figure S9. Spatial distribution of the Emberger Q1 classes for the RCP8.5 scenario and 2041-2060 period over the phytogeographical zones of Greece.

Figure S10. Q1 classes' relative surface (1.0=100%) per phytogeographical zone for the RCP8.5 scenario and 2041-2060 period.

Table S5. The percentage (%) of the Q1 classes' coverage per phytogeographical zone for the RCP8.5 scenario and 2041-2060 period.

	SeAr	SuHu	Hu
Pe	4.8	93.8	1.4
NC	74.4	25.6	0.0
EAe	4.5	95.5	0.0
lol	0.0	85.7	14.3
EC	41.9	55.6	2.5
KK	0.5	82.8	16.7
NAe	80.7	19.3	0.0
KiK	80.9	19.1	0.0
WAe	76.1	23.9	0.0
NE	92.6	7.4	0.0
SPi	3.7	93.8	2.5
StE	20.3	79.1	0.6
NPi	1.1	86.5	12.4

Table S6. The percentage (%) of the Q2 classes' coverage per phytogeographical zone for the 1970-2000 period.

	SeAr-Ho	SeAr-Te	SuHu-Ho	SuHu-Te	SuHu-Co	Hu-Te	Hu-Co	Hu-Cd	Hu-VCd	PeHu-Co	PeHu-Cd	PeHu-VCd	SeAr-Co	SeAr-Cd	SeAr-VCd	SuHu-Cd	SuHu-VCd	PeHu-Te
Pe	0.3	3.3	0.0	56.7	19.3	1.1	13.7	5.3	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
NC	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	21.4	9.6	0.0	36.3	26.0	0.0
EAe	0.0	0.6	8.3	68.4	21.5	1.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
lol	0.0	0.0	0.0	16.8	0.0	49.7	30.6	0.1	0.0	2.4	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
EC	0.8	5.1	2.7	20.9	20.4	2.8	6.0	4.9	1.3	0.4	0.1	0.1	9.9	3.2	0.0	14.3	7.1	0.0
KK	11.3	0.0	37.5	25.2	0.0	20.4	0.9	0.0	0.0	3.9	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.4
NAe	0.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	67.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	15.7	0.0	0.0	13.8	0.5	0.0
KiK	1.0	73.7	0.0	23.9	1.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
WAe	0.0	43.6	0.0	23.9	30.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.0	0.0
NE	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	23.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	26.6	9.8	0.0	32.1	8.4	0.0
SPi	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.9	21.9	3.8	23.6	19.2	8.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	14.6	2.7	0.0
StE	0.0	10.1	0.0	37.5	31.5	1.1	4.9	9.3	1.3	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.1	0.0	0.0
NPi	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	10.2	22.4	8.4	2.9	1.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	16.9	37.8	0.0

Table S7. The percentage (%) of the Q2 classes' coverage per phytogeographical zone for the RCP4.5 and 2021-2040 period.

	SeAr-Ho	SeAr-Te	SuHu-Ho	SuHu-Te	SuHu-Co	Hu-Te	Hu-Co	Hu-Cd	PeHu-Co	PeHu-Cd	SeAr-Co	SeAr-Cd	SuHu-Cd	SuHu-VCd	Hu-VCd	Ar-Ho	SeAr-VHo	Hu-Ho	PeHu-Te	PeHu-VCd
Pe	9.1	2.1	13.4	59.5	4.1	2.2	8.9	0.6	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
NC	0.0	19.8	0.0	0.9	21.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	22.6	2.3	27.6	5.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
EAe	0.9	9.5	38.0	50.5	0.8	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
lol	0.0	0.0	7.4	34.2	0.0	55.3	3.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
EC	4.7	19.7	6.9	25.9	14.5	3.9	3.8	1.5	0.1	0.0	8.5	0.6	8.1	1.3	0.3	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0
KK	26.9	0.0	48.4	2.7	0.0	15.4	0.2	0.0	1.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.3	2.0	0.2	0.0
NAe	0.0	58.5	0.0	20.4	19.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
KiK	63.7	26.1	1.7	8.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
WAe	0.8	67.7	0.0	27.1	4.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
NE	0.0	34.6	0.0	4.0	22.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	27.2	1.6	8.4	1.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
SPi	0.0	0.0	0.0	29.8	28.6	13.5	10.8	7.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	8.2	0.0	1.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
StE	2.4	17.9	0.0	56.4	15.8	0.9	2.7	3.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
NPi	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	14.7	6.9	20.5	6.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	41.6	6.0	3.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0

Table S8. The percentage (%) of the Q2 classes' coverage per phytogeographical zone for the RCP4.5 and 2041-2060 period.

	SeAr-VHo	SeAr-Ho	SeAr-Te	SuHu-Ho	SuHu-Te	SuHu-Co	Hu-Te	Hu-Co	Hu-Cd	PeHu-Co	PeHu-Cd	SeAr-Co	SeAr-Cd	SuHu-Cd	SuHu-VCd	Ar-Ho	SuHu-VHo	Hu-Ho	Hu-VCd	PeHu-Te
Pe	0.0	14.0	0.7	22.3	52.8	2.9	1.5	5.6	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
NC	0.0	0.0	26.3	0.0	1.3	22.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	23.9	1.9	20.6	3.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
E Ae	0.0	12.8	15.3	35.5	36.2	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
lol	0.0	0.0	0.0	22.5	43.5	0.0	32.9	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
EC	1.2	6.8	23.9	8.7	23.9	13.1	2.9	2.1	0.7	0.1	0.0	8.2	0.5	6.6	0.8	0.2	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.0
KK	19.0	18.4	0.0	44.5	1.0	0.0	12.6	0.4	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0	0.0	0.1
NAe	0.0	0.0	75.0	0.0	10.5	13.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
KiK	0.0	72.3	11.7	0.6	5.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	10.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
WAe	0.0	11.6	62.8	0.0	23.9	1.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
NE	0.0	0.0	49.2	0.0	2.0	16.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	25.0	1.0	6.1	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
SPi	0.0	0.0	2.1	0.0	42.0	31.0	8.1	4.2	3.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	8.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.0
StE	0.0	8.8	17.1	3.4	52.8	13.9	0.3	1.3	1.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
NPi	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.8	28.3	11.3	11.8	2.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	39.5	4.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.6	0.0

Table S9. The percentage (%) of the Q2 classes' coverage per phytogeographical zone for the RCP8.5 and 2021-2040 period.

	SeAr-Ho	SeAr-Te	SuHu-Ho	SuHu-Te	SuHu-Co	Hu-Te	Hu-Co	Hu-Cd	PeHu-Co	PeHu-Cd	SeAr-Co	SeAr-Cd	SuHu-Cd	SuHu-VCd	Ar-Ho	SeAr-VHo	SuHu-VHo	Hu-Ho	Hu-VCd	PeHu-Te
Pe	10.5	1.9	14.4	58.4	5.0	1.8	7.5	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
NC	0.0	18.7	0.0	0.7	16.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	26.0	3.8	27.5	6.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
E Ae	1.3	14.4	38.7	44.6	0.7	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
lol	0.0	0.0	8.5	47.5	0.0	41.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
EC	5.0	19.7	7.0	25.1	13.7	3.1	3.1	1.2	0.1	0.0	9.9	1.1	8.5	1.6	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.0
KK	24.3	0.0	47.4	1.8	0.0	14.2	0.3	0.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.8	0.0	2.5	0.0	0.2
NAe	0.0	65.3	0.0	12.0	21.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	1.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
KiK	67.1	23.7	1.5	7.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
WAe	1.2	68.9	0.0	25.7	4.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
NE	0.0	33.3	0.0	1.9	19.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	32.2	2.9	8.2	1.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
SPi	0.0	0.2	0.0	32.5	31.4	9.6	8.2	5.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.4	0.0
StE	3.0	17.8	0.0	56.5	16.7	0.4	1.7	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0
NPi	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	14.8	6.3	18.4	4.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	44.9	9.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	0.0

Table S10. The percentage (%) of the Q2 classes' coverage per phytogeographical zone for the RCP8.5 and 2041-2060 period.

	Ar-VHo	Ar-Ho	SeAr-VHo	SeAr-Ho	SeAr-Te	SuHu-Ho	SuHu-Te	SuHu-Co	Hu-Te	Hu-Co	Hu-Cd	PeHu-Co	PeHu-Cd	SeAr-Co	SeAr-Cd	SuHu-Cd	SuHu-VCd	SuHu-VHo	Hu-Ho	Hu-VCd
Pe	0.0	0.2	0.0	20.3	1.4	21.6	49.1	3.4	0.6	3.2	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
NC	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	30.5	0.0	1.3	21.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	24.1	2.2	17.8	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0
E Ae	0.0	0.0	1.6	17.9	19.7	33.7	26.9	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0
lol	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	32.3	47.5	0.0	19.7	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
EC	0.1	0.9	1.9	8.7	26.7	9.0	21.5	12.5	2.1	1.2	0.4	0.0	0.0	7.9	0.5	5.8	0.6	0.0	0.1	0.1
KK	0.8	0.0	29.5	15.3	0.0	39.4	1.0	0.0	10.8	0.7	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.2	0.0
NAe	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	78.3	0.0	10.1	11.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
KiK	0.0	29.1	0.0	60.1	7.3	0.4	3.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
WAe	0.0	0.7	0.0	25.9	56.8	0.0	15.7	0.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
NE	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	55.9	0.0	1.5	12.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	23.8	1.0	5.0	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0
SPi	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.3	1.2	46.6	30.6	4.6	2.4	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	8.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3
StE	0.0	2.2	0.0	12.9	19.5	7.1	42.9	12.9	0.2	0.7	1.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
NPi	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.5	36.3	11.4	7.0	1.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	36.3	3.6	0.0	0.0	0.7